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**Changing the Conversation: Towards a Visual Epistemology
in Interpreting Irish Parliamentary Debates**

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CHANGING THE CONVERSATION

Towards a Visual Epistemology in Interpreting Irish Parliamentary Debates

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Abstract

Inspired by the tenets of Drucker's "Graphesis", this paper explores the possibility of using a visual epistemology in interpreting Irish parliamentary debates. In exploring the idiosyncratic nature of political and particularly parliamentary debate, it considers aspects of close, distant and hyper reading, text as structured data, the question of linking language and graphical approaches to the humanities. Taking the example of one day of debate from Dáil Éireann and using data from the Houses of the Oireachtas open data portal, it explores components of political discourse, investigates the meaning that can be taken from those elements and proposes examples of an alternative, visual epistemology as a complementary path to interpreting parliamentary debate.

Digital Artefact

available at: digital.changingconversations.net

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Declaration

This is to certify that the work I am submitting is my own and has not been submitted for another degree, either at University College Cork or elsewhere. All external references and sources are clearly acknowledged and identified within the contents. I have read and understood the regulations of University College Cork concerning plagiarism and intellectual property.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "David Cass". The signature is written in a cursive style and is positioned above a horizontal line.

Introduction

If You Don't Like What's Being Said, Change the Conversation

Even well-known political speech can hold the characteristic of at once being well-known and barely understood. Many people will have at least heard of Dr. Martin Luther King's "I Have a Dream" speech (March on Washington for Jobs and Freedom; Part 17 of 17, 2021), for example, given during the 1963 march on Washington DC, but few will have heard or read it in its entirety and even fewer will have studied its meaning at a micro level. For the vast majority, the interpretation of the speech – its meaning-making – will have come second or third-hand.

Political discourse is all around us; it happens every day on television and radio, in newspapers and magazines and on a massive scale on the new platforms afforded to us through the Internet (Jungherr, Schroeder and Stier, 2019). It can happen when two people meet at a rural bar and it can involve thousands of people at political rallies. It is, quite literally, a ruling force in most people's lives. Yet how much of what informs this discourse is also second or third-hand, potentially disrupting the meaning we take from it? How many of us think we are forming opinions but are just following something we have read, seen or heard?

A subset of this political discourse is parliamentary debate. Perhaps the best-known form of parliamentary proceedings reporting is the Hansard at Westminster, which is also the format of reporting inherited by the Irish Parliament, the Houses of the Oireachtas. In contrast with an increasing proportion of political debate, Hansard is known as a "no-spin zone" (UK Parliament Open Lecture -- The history, workings and future challenges of Hansard, 2013).

The Debates Office in the Houses of the Oireachtas has since the earliest meetings of the Houses recorded the proceedings of parliamentary debate at Leinster House (Oireachtas, 2020a), collected in large format printed

volumes and, since the 1990s, on the Oireachtas website. Aside from a few relatively minor editorial changes, both the format of the debate and its epistemological basis have remained largely the same even as the technology and methods of reporting the debate by the staff of the Debates Office changed and technology and media evolved (Oireachtas, 2020b). People take meaning from political discourse on a personal level but the political conversation informing them is, for the most part, a public act. Political discourse has been reported for centuries in newspapers and on television or radio for decades, while newer social media have served to splinter the discourse even further, potentially making it more difficult than ever for people to interpret meaning from it. If political discourse is constantly changing and the pace of change in the media and technology is at times mind-boggling, is it realistic for the Dáil's Official Report to remain a static textual corpus? Is it even possible for it to change without losing its authority?

The basis of this research is derived from the following passage in Drucker's essay on "Graphesis", or visual forms of knowledge production (Drucker, 2014, p.29):

The tenets of graphesis I am promoting are aligned with the precepts on which McGann proposes interpretation as fundamental to the production of a text. Graphesis is premised on the idea that an image, like a text, is an aesthetic provocation, a field of potentialities, in which a viewer intervenes. Knowledge is not transferred, revealed, or perceived, but is created through a dynamic process. Epistemology describes a way of knowing, not static knowledge.

Political discourse may be one of the first things to come to mind when we think of “interpretation as fundamental” to its production. A political debate is at once performance and promise, an ever-changing and personal conversation between political actors and the people they represent (Slembrouck, 1992).

The text of the Official Report is just one of many reflections of the cultural primacy accorded to the printed word. The printed books are accorded reverence relative to their cost of production and as the default for what has been described as a sacred icon, close reading (Hayles, 2010), whereas the Official Report on the web can be changed with a few keystrokes. These are, however, the same text, or at least *the same interpretation of political debate*. The debates from each day have their own copies produced in PDF, the echo of a printed book. In a time when people swipe on a screen as much as they turn a page, is there room for another way of interpreting this debate, something that moves away from the shadow of the printed word (Hayles, 2016)? Is it even the case that the printed word, the vast tracts of text that each day’s debate produces, can serve to hold back other approaches to meaning-making?

In evaluating the potential of the visual epistemological approach espoused by Drucker, this research will, in a review of literature, consider different types of reading in a digital age, including close, distant and hyper reading, evaluating specifically the different ways in which political discourse can be “read”. It will examine the way text can be structured as data, the manner in which data can be linked and digital methods of text analysis and language processing before investigating broadly how graphical approaches have been used in interrogating data specifically in the digital humanities.

It is intended to investigate the possibility of using a visual epistemological approach to interpreting parliamentary debate by using Dáil debate from a

single day, 11 May 2021, while evaluating data resources that include the PDF “version” of the debate, the Houses of the Oireachtas website and its open data portal.

As part of its evolving work practices, the Debates Office and the Oireachtas as a whole has embraced the structuring of data in the organisation. It produces structured data in forms influenced by Berners-Lee’s vision of open and linked data (5 Star Linked Data - Government Linked Data (GLD) Working Group Wiki, 2021). By leveraging this structure, it may be possible to at the very least suggest a visual epistemological approach to the Dáil’s political debates. The research process will compare the current text-based “reading” of the day’s debate with possible visual interpretations of the corpus and document those interpretations with the digital artefact at digital.changingconversations.net.

Drucker’s vision for a visual epistemology is ambitious. As she states, an image is not self-evident and people must learn to read even the simplest of maps by learning their codes and internal language (Drucker, 2014).

Learning to read a debate in the absence of - or at least without complete reliance on - words may be even more ambitious. Drucker references interpretation, as indicated by McGann, as being fundamental to the production of text but a visual epistemology may require a re-evaluation of how people make this interpretation; moreover, it may require a *willingness* to make this re-evaluation.

In a perfect world, people would derive their own meaning but some fear that meaning-making itself is now breaking down (Can’t Get You Out of My Head (2021) - Part 2: Shooting and F**king are the Same Thing, 2021). We have long since moved from a time when meaning was derived from reading books or listening to the radio and television alone. Media have changed and their forms have ballooned in number. The manner in which

we speak, read, interact and derive our everyday meaning changes at blinding speed. If conversations can span continents in seconds, it may be time to change how we take meaning from those conversations.

Literature Review

Reading and Marking Text

Reading text, at its core, is both personal or subjective yet beholden to its universality. As argued by Drucker (2017, p. 634), reading “is an act of self-production” and a “shifting” process. If the core function of the Debates Office of the Houses of the Oireachtas is to produce “the *written* record of everything that is *said* in public sittings of the Houses of the Oireachtas and their parliamentary committees”, (Oireachtas, 2020b), there is an extra dimension to reading what was, at least initially, verbal expression, now produced and read digitally for the most part, yet deeply indebted to its historical editorial traditions, born in print.

The Official Report is a bank of data but these data are in the main text, so does this mean the report comes with all the cultural sandboxing that reading texts can bring? McGann (2015), explores the myriad facets to be “seen, registered and understood” even in considering the documentary level of reading, and in discussing the marking of texts argues that there must be social, historical and other characteristics inherent in such processes; in essence, reading text must regard both the text and the reader as “co-dependent” and we cannot have one without the other. Moreover, Hayles (2016) explores the inherent instability in meaning, which she posits is destabilised “every time someone offers a new reading”, leading to the suggestion that interpretations of text, or at least the meaning that can be ascribed to texts, can be in a constant state of flux affected even with the act of reading. Does it follow then, that how we read can affect political text and, by extension, the meaning we derive from texts like the Official Report?

McGann imagines a digital process that allows a person to “mark and store maps of textual fields”, facilitated by a process of “reading”, in order to study them and compare with other such maps. This, he argues, can be

done in order to short-circuit a number of preconceptions about the textual condition and, more important, escape interpretive dichotomies like “text” and “reader” or, by extension, subjectivity and objectivity.

Pierazzo (2015), in examining the digital marking of texts through the Text Encoding Initiative, TEI, describes digital editing as a “consolidated reality”. With specific reference to the TEI, she considers how the transformation of “the editor into an encoder” can bring about improvements in presenting or re-presenting the material; she argues that text encoding applied in a digital environment has the potential to free textual scholars from constraints of the medium and, importantly, meet the requirements of different readerships. In this way, perhaps, the publication of the Dáil’s Official Report is ahead in the game, as both the debate and other related datasets, including votes and the text of legislation, are marked up within semantic web standards and with consideration to linked and open data aspirations.

Case Study:

Oireachtas Ontology on GitHub @ <https://github.com/Oireachtas/ontology>

The ontology developed for use with data produced by the Oireachtas has its basis in the web ontology language, OWL (OWL - Semantic Web Standards, 2021), with extensive use of European Legislative Identifier, ELI (ELI - EUR-Lex, 2021), ontology elements; the CEN MetaLex open XML interchange format (CEN MetaLex - Open XML Interchange Format for Legal and Legislative Resources, 2021), which standardises methods for references to law in XML; and the Akoma Ntoso XML schema for use specifically with parliamentary, legislative and judiciary documentation (Akoma Ntoso, n.d.). OWL uses the resource description framework, RDF, syntax that is the standard model for data interoperability for the web, and although this has not been integrated in a complete way with the Oireachtas

ontology, it nonetheless shares elements and the aspiration of linking open data. The Oireachtas ontology can be seen in OWL format at

<https://github.com/Oireachtas/ontology/blob/master/data/oireachtas.owl>.

The markup used specifically for Oireachtas debate body, as opposed to generalised metadata used for these debates, legislation and votes, is detailed at <https://github.com/Oireachtas/ontology/wiki/Debates-body>.

Marking up this type of text should, of course, be easier than the marking of the texts with which the TEI is normally engaged (Projects Using the TEI – TEI: Text Encoding Initiative, 2021), for example. The Official Report is now “born digital”, produced initially as XML before being distributed to digital platforms and printed in physical forms as necessary. If the “marking” of the text can be accomplished according to the Oireachtas ontology, and this is done in tandem with the Official Report’s production, rather than as a separate and following process, other considerations in deriving meaning from these political debates remain, least of all the “linking” of language across such an expansive body of text.

Linking Language

The Oireachtas ontology means the Official Report is already marked up with the semantic web in mind but why were elements of the ELI not fully implemented, for example? It has been argued that linked data are merely a way of publishing data in a way that facilitates connection; a happy union is not guaranteed and the semantic web and linked data may either “combine in a fascinating development of digital infrastructure, computer reasoning, interpretation and digital collaboration, or instead participate in a dismal collision, leaving only a mechanical meaningless shell in [their] wake.” (Oldman, Doerr and Gradmann, 2015).

On the face of it, the political sphere, or at least the sphere of public service, is an appropriate jumping-off point for linked and open data. Shadbolt et al. (2012), for example, detail several examples of such data put to use, including a process linking six UK datasets covering the work of UK Members of Parliament, the UK Parliament as a whole, crime, mortality and health statistics and geographical data.

Work from Russo and Wiberg (2010) indicates issues that may arise even when trying to compare what are, *prima facie*, similar objects or research considerations, such as questions put down in parliaments. In attempting to compare parliamentary questions across multiple parliaments, they indicate that such work is “complicated not only by the difficulties in collecting comparable data but also by the lack of agreed criteria to classify different forms of parliamentary questions”, so does implementation of text markup such as that evidenced by the Oireachtas present any avenue to improvement?

Van Aggelen et al.’s work (2017) offers a glimpse at how such a vision might be implemented in a parliamentary setting. Their *LinkedEP* (AVA, 2018) presents a linked open data translation of the verbatim reports of the plenary meetings of the European Parliament, integrated with other databases and the results of which are available in a SPARQL endpoint. A discussion on uses includes several examples involving the comparison of the discourse of political groups.

There is not, however, a conclusive argument that using linked and open data in this way can be a panacea in extracting meaning from political discourse. If, as Oldman, Doerr and Gradmann (2015) argue, linked data methods can only express, relate and exchange meaning effectively if humanists learn how to express their concepts, methods and processes in formalised and detailed way, Unsworth’s argument (2013) that the

representations of the semantic web should be produced by people trained in the humanities takes on renewed urgency.

Case Study: DiLiPad and LiPad @ <https://www.lipad.ca>

The Digging into Linked Parliamentary Data, DiLiPad, (Beelen et al., 2017), project was born of an investigation of how computational techniques could be used to investigate the “big data” of parliamentary proceedings in the UK, Canada and the Netherlands, aiming to facilitate comparative analysis of the history of parliamentary discourse. The project archive is available at <https://blog.history.ac.uk/tag/digging-into-linked-parliamentary-data/> and the white paper is available at https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6544/1/DiLiPaD_final_report_1.pdf. Of note is the fact that as part of its digitisation process, the project annotated the XML using a bespoke schema following Dublin Core metadata guidelines while reusing modules from the TEI wherever possible.

The LiPad (Linked Parliamentary Data) project is the most fully realised elements of DiLiPad and exists as a search platform for the record of Canadian parliamentary texts, the Canadian Hansard. Of note, along with its search facility, is the making available of data as a PostgreSQL dump on a monthly basis, the XML of the entire Hansard dataset from 1901 to 1993 in compressed file format and other or supplementary data.

Figure 1: Detail of LiPad query of Canadian Parliament debate from 11 May 2021

Conspicuous by its absence, perhaps, is the wider embrace of this approach to enhance interoperability. Many of the linked data projects described by Shadbolt et al. appear mothballed and projects such as DiLiPad and the fruits of van Aggelen et al.'s research do not appear to have gained momentum, to say the least. There may be technical obstacles and the deleterious effects of apathy cannot be discounted but, as one might infer from Oldman, Doerr and Gradmann, is it possible that the union of the semantic web and linked data could amount to a zero sum because meaning is lost in their collision?

Reading Politics – Data to Capta

The Official Report is a political text, born of political interaction and political relationships. Monroe, and Schrodt (2017, p.351) argue “text is arguably the most pervasive – and certainly the most persistent – artifact of political behaviour.”. Baumann, Debus and Müller (2015), in analysing speeches given by Dáil Deputies on abortion legislation in 2001 and 2013, indicate that, in the main, contributions to the Official Report tend to reflect

the preferences of their constituents, as this maximises their chance of renomination and re-election to the national parliament, although they may also express personal convictions. In focusing on the parliamentary speeches from two specific debates dealing with a broadly similar legislative effort, the authors were able to estimate the positions of Deputies by applying a word scores scaling model (Benoit and Laver, 2003), part of which compares word frequencies in texts. It is interesting that Laver and Benoit's work from the early 21st century (Laver and Benoit, 2002) refers to the "labour-intensive" nature of the coding to be done; this research would have been done very shortly after the first publication of debate archives following their digitisation in the 1990s.

It is argued by Lauderdale and Herzog (2016), however, that approaches to measuring political disagreement from text data tend to perform poorly except in cases where the texts are narrowly selected, discuss the same matters or are written in the same style. The Official Report at least has consistency of editorial style but is necessarily broad-ranging, and Lauderdale and Herzog, in examining data primarily focused on political disagreement from both the Irish Dáil and United States Senate, indicate that "given sufficiently rich data" – and, presumably, the data coming from a single database such as the Official Report could only be beneficial – positions could be measured across topics. As they note, recovering such data can be laborious because of the nature of word usage but it is nonetheless integral to any study of position taking because it is a main element in the strategies adopted by parliamentarians in both their political and electoral environments. Essentially, omitting parliamentary speech from the study of politics is to ignore what is, if not one of the largest, one of the most important corpora in the political sphere.

Goet (2019), realises this in using 6.2 million records of parliamentary speeches from the UK between 1811 and 2015 in order to measure polarisation through text analysis, although it is interesting that an identified weakness in this approach is in ignoring “dimensionality”, meaning political disagreements cannot be considered at the “granular” level.

Monroe and Schrodt (2017) discuss the political trade-off between statistical modelling of this type and the study of language in considering automated analysis of political texts. The aforementioned studies rely on statistical modelling but Toomey (2015), for example, in considering linguistic applications of political debate specifically within the Dáil’s chamber, identifies purpose beyond the superficiality of political positions for reasons of election; these include functions of “law-making, legitimisation and control”. Interestingly, Toomey identifies elements that may not be easily identified by statistical modelling approaches, such as heckling as strategy or the importance of questioning in holding politicians in charge to account. In addition, Martin (2011) considers how the polarity of that power dynamic, and, presumably, its association assumptions, can be reversed with the possibility that parliamentary questions tabled by Deputies are used by some to justify their work to constituents, essentially as a vote-earning strategy. He furthers this work with parliamentary questions specifically related to foreign affairs, identifying the questions asked by parliamentarians as a “potentially fertile tool to uncover the behaviour of individual parliamentarians” (Martin, 2013), but can political meaning be best divined by statistical methods, machine-assisted methods such as natural language processing, a combination of at least the logic behind both or another approach completely?

The primary difficulty in moving beyond recorded speech and texts as data to *capta* is that it is unstructured (Maseda, 2021), although most texts share

at least some common characteristics, including length or word construction or frequency qualities. As Maseda indicates, quantitative analyses may use methods that bear some relation to the statistically led work outlined above in order to provide measurements or comparisons, for example, and an evolution of this type of text analysis might lead to other branches to ascribe metatextual qualities to the text data, including sentiment analysis.

Some research (Rheault et al., 2016), meanwhile, may have tackled the weakness identified by Goet of sacrificing granularity at the altar of mass data analysis using a sentiment analysis approach. Taking a similar approach to Goet in a mass textual analysis of Hansard records, Rheault et al. consider the measurement of “emotion” in parliamentary debate. Interestingly, their approach uses text as marked up following linked open data standards as part of the Digging into Linked Parliamentary Data, Dilipad, project previously outlined, where the data are broken down to token level.

Case Study:

The Proceedings of the Old Bailey @ <https://www.oldbaileyonline.org>

This website, hosted by the Digital Humanities Institute at Sheffield University, has a fully searchable digitised collection of legal texts detailing the proceedings of the Old Bailey, including 190,000 pages of proceedings, along with other digitised documents, including images and maps. It is at least somewhat analogous to the Official Report’s corpus in that its data are legal or quasi-legal and their use at scale is facilitated by the interrelated processes of digitisation and marking up of historical texts according to a defined schema. The project’s XML files and other resources are available directly and through application programming interfaces.

Of interest is the myriad projects that have used the data on the website as a basis for deriving further meaning. These include connectedhistories.org

and londonlives.org websites, the latter of which makes available a wide range of digitised and fully searchable primary sources detailing the everyday lives of people in London between 1690 and 1800; the Old Bailey proceedings are part of a repository of eight archives and 15 datasets. The most interesting aspects of use, however, may be those that go beyond a presentation of texts or data to a re-presentation. For example, the Digital Panopticon project at digitalpanopticon.org has a visualisation gallery for data. The Old Bailey Voices project at oldbaileyvoices.org, meanwhile, building on the Old Bailey Online dataset, proposes to illustrate “how a range of tools for textual and data analysis, might be combined to create a working ‘macroscope’ ... where ‘big data’ can be explored both at scale and at the level of the single datum. It is an ambitious aim and the reward may outweigh the risk to meaning.

Figure 2: Detail of visualisation from the Digital Panopticon

(Natural) Language (Processing)

A nub in the argument, therefore, appears to be the distinction between seeing political text as data, as is arguably evidenced in statistically led work, or as something closer to what Drucker had in mind (Drucker, 2011) in redefining all data as *capta* - something to be taken and constructed - as it could be argued those working on the Old Bailey Voices project are doing. If we are to explore a digital process along the lines of what McGann proposes, it may be, as Jockers and Underwood (2015) posit, that we can take lessons from the disparate areas of natural language processing and machine learning. They explore the possibilities of harnessing the technical efficiency of text mining procedures and applying natural language processing toolkits. Even the term “natural language processing” might be seen as intrinsically paradoxical, however. Drucker (2017), for example, argues that processing does not equate to reading, which is “ideational, hermeneutic, generative and productive”. In exploring distant reading, moreover, she considers how even if algorithms make decisions in such processes, the algorithms themselves are based on models designed as interpretive acts. Drucker seems to consider digital tools like Voyant Tools (Voyant Tools, 2021) as “processing” rather than “reading”, arguing that the natural language processes demonstrate weakness in that complex understanding is absent from the analytics required when dealing with language; as she mentions, “meaning is what language does”.

So is there danger in the creation of “data-driven rather than knowledge-driven” processes, as Kitchin (2014) explores in hypothesising a reflexive and contextually nuanced epistemology? The Dáil’s Official Report arguably shares Kitchin’s characterisation of big data as “being generated continuously, seeking to be exhaustive and fine-grained in scope, and flexible and scalable in its production”.

Hayles (2007) and others address hyper reading, described in Bolter (2016) as a potential hindrance to deep thinking. If it is the case that reflective reading and writing can no longer claim the centrality it had in the past, as Bolter argues, and where one community of readers and writers has been superseded by interlocking communities, where does it leave the act of reading (political) debates, current and historical, in a digital age?

If Kitchin's argument that big data represent an opportunity for scholars arising from "massive quantities of very rich social, cultural, economic, political and historical data", the proposal for a critical examination of the epistemological implications of such data and the building of a more reflexive epistemological approach seems logical, especially as a rebuttal to the argument that digital tools tend more to weak surface analysis rather than deeper insight.

Favro et al. (2016) refer to a "lack of deep thinking", as mentioned by Nicholas Carr, and how deep reading has come to be seen by "digital natives" (as opposed to "digital immigrants") as an educational necessity rather than something done for pleasure. Yet on the other side of this Janus face are core concepts of the digital humanities, those with which digital natives are arguably most comfortable, including "fluid textuality", "ubiquitous scholarship" and "distributed knowledge production". As Favro et al. argue, these terms conceptualise "shifts in cultural production and humanistic inquiry" *precisely because they are digital*.

Re-Presenting Reading

Johanna Drucker's idea of graphesis (Drucker, 2014) is well known in digital humanities. She also reflects on the relationship between graphical approaches to aspects of interpretation and knowledge production (Drucker, 2015), exploring various methods of presenting data, such as

textual data as exemplified by the Official Report, as well as the “mediated experience of the user interface”, noting that there are tensions in interface “between offering cues for behaviour and presenting an information structure”. Drucker (2016) also notes the intellectual and epistemological challenges in using visualisations – most notably that a visualisation can be “in a relation of equivalence or identity with that which it claims to represent” – but advocates visual epistemology as “essential” nonetheless because not everything we see can be remediated to language.

Drucker (2020) expounds on a visual epistemology approach by indicating that images have no simple correlation to language but that like any form of human expression, including natural and formal language, visual imagery becomes more stable when coding is incorporated with a linguistic gloss, for example. If images are not self-evident, Drucker argues, but we learn to decipher the codes associated with them, the concern is not as much that data such as political debate would not be understood in graphical form but whether knowledge production can take place in the same way as it does in close reading processes, for example. Is the question, therefore, not whether there should be a visual epistemological approach to reading political debate but whether there is value in it?

If political discourse is first a verbal and even visual performance, could it be argued that putting this debate into written form is in itself a transformative process? If so, is it merely cultural or historical capital that keeps the written corpus, and potentially the PDF form of debate that mirrors the printed debates, holding position at the apex of cultural significance? It is, after all, itself just a version of the discourse, although one held in the highest esteem.

Drucker also argues that even material that is born digital impersonates analogue counterparts. This, at the very least, holds back potential

alternative readings of discourse and at worst perpetuates barriers to the making of meaning.

People read digital texts as PDFs to replicate the pages of books; the Dáil's Official Report is, rather redundantly, published as a PDF to accompany the text as it appears online. Digital music is still presented, at least superficially, in album formats or "playlists" that hark back to mixtapes. Digital photographs are still stored in "albums", despite advances in facial recognition for organisational purposes, for example. What more is possible if we remove analogue shackles from a digital corpus?

Finally, is it possible to rationalise the tensions that seem inevitable if we follow Drucker's apparent approach in advocating a visual epistemology, as described by Simanowski (Drucker, 2016), of bringing relativism into a world of quantifying methods? Can the computational methods researching parliamentary discourse tending towards quantitative and statistical approaches be reconciled to efforts to discern meaning on a humanistic level as can be seen with the Old Bailey Online project? Could this reconciliation be achieved through digital methods, achieved with a visual epistemology facilitated by marking text?

Epistemological and Methodological Statement

Speak. Write.

The Official Report is at its core a paradox in itself, of sorts, being a written account of what is said in political discourse in the Houses of the Oireachtas. Both written and spoken, its meaning may lie somewhere in between. In common with many parliaments of Westminster heritage, the Official Report has nevertheless come to be regarded as the “definitive account of parliamentary proceedings” (Edwards, 2016, p.145); moreover, the “Hansard” of Westminster has been described as “the ultimate ‘no-spin’ zone” in reporting parliamentary events (UK Parliament Open Lecture -- The history, workings and future challenges of Hansard, 2013). If the account is definitive, as Edwards argues, which version is most “definitive”, as parliamentary reports, created electronically as XML documents, are now published in tandem with video files and in parallel to other discourses, such as on social media? Does the printed record trump all of these, and if so, why?

Edwards questions whether Hansard-style parliamentary reports can be a true “no-spin” zone when words spoken by parliamentarians are transformed into a written text, edited by reporting staff and even subject to a correction process by the public representatives in a retrospective application of meaning; the debates of the Oireachtas may remain on an “unrevised” footing for years, for example. McGann (2015) speaks of the myriad facets to be “registered and understood” even in reading a document and Hayles (2016) referenced the instability of meaning, affected even by the act of reading. Despite the assumption of stability, definition and authority, these political debates, even those captured via the Official Report, are snapshots of a process of flux.

Write. See.

If the act of editing creates new texts that present or “(re)present” work (Shillingsburg, 2006), even with the provision of a written record in a “substantially verbatim” form, the Debates Office must be subject to the questions asked of any edited organ. In considering linguistic aspects of Hansard-style reporting, for example, it is clear that transcribers and editors “omit performance characteristics of spoken language” (Mollin, 2007, p. 187), meaning what is written down can only be a *version* of what was said to begin with. This is all the more interesting when we consider studies (Rheault et al., 2016) specifically seeking to divine measures of elements like emotion, more typically seen in speech and one of the most likely facets to disappear when debates are written.

If discrepancies are noted more often between the report and video clips on social media, is it possible the legitimacy of the Official Report will be diluted? As ways of accessing both historical and current political debates increase with digital advances, and as methods of analysis grow further in reach and detail, is there a danger the Official Report will lose authority? Debates Office staff see its archive role as an overriding motivation of the work, indicating “the main purpose of the Official Report lies in its importance as a historical record of parliamentary debate” (O’Donnell, 2013, p. 97). Indeed, the Houses of the Oireachtas website indicates that “fundamentally, the Debates Office has been doing the same job since its establishment in 1922” (Oireachtas, 2020b). The text is produced following editorial guidelines that have remained mostly static throughout its history, lending it legitimacy in the face of newer and more immediate forms of media. If the printed tomes have remained reassuringly familiar, what has changed is the underlying production process; what was once a typed workflow produced in triplicate pages is now digital, with automated

marking up of the debate as it is reported and application of the Akoma Ntoso XML schema and web ontology during an extract, transform and load sequence for publication on the web. If the Official Report is still used as it has been since inception a century ago, are these valuable additions to its publication process being ignored? More important, is their potential for meaning-making being left behind? The marking up of parliamentary debates facilitates the application of digital tools in their reading, both in close, distant and hyper forms. Close reading may have cultural primacy but surely the application of such digital tools can only add to the extraction of meaning from this body of political debate, even in a complementary process.

Speak. See.

If, as O’Sullivan argues, the “dynamics ... of communication” have been altered by the emergence of technology because of a greater ability to engage with the public (O’Sullivan, Long and Mattson, 2016, p.387), it would appear incumbent on the Debates Office, as a tool for keeping the Oireachtas to account, to embrace changing dynamics in the different forms of media. Schreibman, for example, speaks about mass digitisation and the “social” edition (Schreibman, 2013), albeit in reference to scholarly editing, and the reporting of events in the Oireachtas may not be immune to such a phenomenon. For example, the usefulness of social media and digital platforms was noted in the 2016 general election (Gallagher and Marsh, 2016) and in 2020 Sinn Féin gained a large amount of first-preference votes when it “won the social media campaign” (Little, 2021, p.716). Moreover, it has been argued that any increased ability to communicate laterally and quickly mobilise through digital platforms can be a powerful tool (Jones, 2016); this is a concept not alien to digital humanities, of course. The

Official Report has historically been available as a printed book but there has been a shift in authority to the report as it is “printed” on the web. The text of debates, along with other data from the Oireachtas, including legislation, votes and parliamentary questions, are available at the Oireachtas open data portal at data.oireachtas.ie but the data appear to be used meagrely.

It is intended in this research to harness the heretofore underused marking up of the Official Report of Dáil Éireann to investigate different forms of interpreting the debate following the visual epistemology espoused by Drucker. It is vital to avoid being tool-led when dealing with such large datasets because of the risk of nuance being lost. Nevertheless, although the printed report – and even the PDF as its electronic form – appears to hold a position of authority, the interpolation of visualisations of *the same data*, facilitated by the marking of text and its products in the form of XML and JSON, may serve to fortify the authority of the Official Report in the face of myriad digital competition.

Methods

The Official Report

The Official Report of the Houses of the Oireachtas is a continuously updated corpus comprising a written record of debates occurring in Dáil Éireann, Seanad Éireann and various committees or parliamentary bodies. It is made available primarily through the Debates Office website at <https://www.oireachtas.ie/en/debates/find/> and the text of the debates is usually uploaded within several hours of the debate happening and after the report has gone through a multistage editorial process.

The Official Report has a corpus dating back to the First Dáil more than a century ago and large amounts of debate are added with every sitting day of the Houses.

Once they have gone through the editorial process, debates in the Official Report are published to the web, facilitated by its form as XML, with the structured data made available on the Oireachtas open data API (Oireachtas, 2021c), along with other structured data in the Oireachtas, including those relating to Members, constituencies, votes, etc., for retrieval and reuse outside of the Oireachtas website.

The simplest way to retrieve the text of a debate is to perform a search of the Debates Office website and a PDF of the entire day's debate can usually be downloaded in tandem with viewing the returned results as web pages for text-based queries.

The Oireachtas open data API is a fulfilment of the EU Open Data Directive (DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/ 1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL - of 20 June 2019 - on open data and the re-use of public sector information, n.d.) that encourages the making available of public sector information for reuse. REST queries may be made via an Elasticsearch back end to return datasets within specific parameters, with the structured data returned as JSONs, providing much more flexibility than

website resources outlined above. Details of uniform resource indicators, URIs, for debates, Members and other information also allow the possibility of further customisation or refining of data searches. The more technical approach to search and data retrieval leaves the possibility to yield far more versatile datasets. For the purposes of this research, data will be taken from one sitting day of the Dáil, as this should be broad enough to discern patterns while keeping data wrangling to a manageable level. An approach for a typical sitting day should in theory be open to scaling or further customisation.

Accessing

Accessing the Houses of the Oireachtas REST API can be done in several ways. Command line scripts can be used with cURL, the command line tool and library, and this is at once the most powerful and customisable search strategy for returning JSONs with very specific data. This method can also be incorporated into platforms like Tableau and Observable d3.js JavaScript library notebooks. The Oireachtas open data portal has a bundled interface description language interface for quickly making REST queries in Swagger/OpenAPI, and an application such as Postman can provide a GUI while being more versatile than the interface on the Oireachtas open data portal.

Coding

Proprietary data visualisation software such as Tableau Desktop can plug in directly to the Oireachtas API to make REST queries with third-party web connector software at the expense of outputs that might not be easily used or shared outside the software's ecosystem. For this reason, it is proposed

to use openly available visualisation platforms such as RAW Graphs, Flourish, and the d3.js library through Observable notebooks unless the results and data can be shared publicly in some form, such as through Tableau Public.

A code editor such as Sublime Text would be appropriate to check JSON and XML data and it has built-in features to verify code and reduce the risk of introducing syntax errors. To this end, websites such as <http://jsonformatter.org/> can also be used where necessary for validating code in real time, for example.

Structuring

The text of the Official Report is structured with XML metatags using the Akoma Ntoso schema and a custom web ontology specialised for parliamentary and legislative documents, meaning both the JSON data returned from the Oireachtas API and the XML documents within are structured so as to allow data collation or query based on specific terms, including date, Chamber, debate type and speaker, among others, with entities such as party, speaker and House having URIs to eliminate duplication or confusion, while at the same time making it easier to relate entities via these URIs.

OpenRefine is an open source alternative to Tableau Prep Builder, which itself works seamlessly with Tableau Desktop, but at the cost of a slightly less intuitive GUI for working with larger files or combining datasets. Data from the Debates Office should not need much alteration because of its excellent structure so any required data cleaning will probably take the form of removing extraneous data and combining datasets where necessary.

Extracting

It is intended to consider, among others, methods of close reading, distant and hyper reading, as well as network and hierarchy analysis of debates with digital tools.

The structured nature of the Oireachtas debate data may also lend itself to being combined with other structured data, including linked data from other sources of political discourse. Political text may lend itself to network and hierarchy analysis, which can be studied with Gephi or Cytoscape. Tools such as Google Cloud Natural Language API or MeaningCloud may achieve a targeted analysis of a text corpus, and there are also tools such as Voyant Tools to provide a one-stop shop for several methods of text analysis.

Making

Making meaning from the large corpus of political text that is the Official Report of the Houses of the Oireachtas can never be a simple process. The body of text is so large and the intricacies of political debate so great, it is essentially impossible, even with digital tools or visualisations, to distil its complicated meaning.

Instead of making meaning from the corpus, therefore, it is more appropriate for this project to be about helping to build meaning. It is about helping to interpret vast quantities of data - text in the case of the Official Report - that themselves contain the political meaning making of public representatives and the people they represent. This process is not about presenting political meaning making as a *fait accompli* but re-presenting it with digital tools accessible to members of the public who wish to make use of them in the spirit of building that is foundational to the digital humanities (Ramsay, 2013).

Process

Publication of the Debate and Scope of Research

Scoping

The debates of the Houses of the Oireachtas are compiled by the staff of the Debates Office, comprising a team of reporters, editors and clerical staff. As indicated, we know the report as published is merely a version of the parliamentary debate both because of its metamorphosis from a verbal to written form and the editorial interventions of the Debates Office staff. Nevertheless, and taking into account the Edwards argument that it is a “definitive” account of parliamentary proceedings, for the purposes of this paper it is appropriate to use the Dáil’s Official Report as published as the baseline text. A provisional version of the debate – “the blacks”, in reference to when the editorial process was paper-based - is made available on an internal corporate server while the editorial process is being completed, usually within several hours of a debate occurring, or early the following day if the session ends late in the evening. After this, the report is “officially” published to the web, initially in an iterative process throughout a sitting day until completion. A separate but similar process of publication is used for replies to written parliamentary questions for each Dáil sitting day.

For the specific purposes of this research, it is intended to restrict the amount of debate to be studied to the Official Report for one sitting day of Dáil Éireann, No. 6 of Volume 1006, 11 May 2021. The research will incorporate both the plenary session and the accompanying replies to written questions for the sitting day. This amounts to approximately 8.5 hours of spoken debate, totalling almost 80,000 words, and 958 written questions and replies.

It was decided to use the debate for the sitting day in question because it is a typical and varied example of business carried out in the Dáil. The debate

comprised questions to both the Taoiseach and a Minister, statements, Private Members' business involving a formal motion and several procedural elements. No legislation was discussed on the day in question, however, and in particular both Committee and Report Stages of legislation - where amendments would be discussed and potentially voted on - could change the dynamic of debates. However, Committee and Report Stage debates do not typically make up a large proportion of the Dáil's plenary business, so it was decided that a day without such debate would still provide useful initial results.

A single day of debate is complete and self-contained but the process for a single day could be scaled to a sitting week, usually comprising three days, or even a longer period because the processes and debate procedures are the same or similar. In addition, it should be possible to apply the principles in working with data from the Dáil on a single sitting day to debate from Seanad Éireann and committees as necessary in future research.

Versions

There is an initial question of which "version" of the debate is to be used.

For the debate of 11 May, the version published to the web is at

<https://www.oireachtas.ie/en/debates/debate/dail/2021-05-11/>, with

different sections of the debate available at addresses deriving from this main page, such as the Private Members' debate at

<https://www.oireachtas.ie/en/debates/debate/dail/2021-05-11/12/>.

On the main debate page there is also a version of the debate published as

PDF at <https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/mul@/main.pdf> and a link to the video of the complete

proceedings, although both of these are added to the main page many

days after the initial publication of the text of the debate in this HTML form.

The question may not be problematic in a technical sense as both the HTML for the web page and the PDF derive from an XML document, available at <https://data.oireachtas.ie/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/mul@/main.xml>. There remains, however, the question of cultural authority and the primacy of “printed text”; if the PDF is derived from the XML document, for example, is its only function to lend the authority of the form of the printed book, something that may be more “tangible” for people, even in its digital form?

As the XML document is the “primary” version of the debate after the extract, transform and load process to the Oireachtas website, and the document from which the PDF and web pages are derived, it is intended to use this as the primary corpus for investigation, with some reference to and use of other forms. There is no equivalent single XML document for the replies to written parliamentary questions and instead there are XML documents for individual question groups and replies. The web page structure is also slightly different from that seen with the plenary debate.

The question of the cultural primacy of books is valid nonetheless. However, daily books – printed copies of single days of debate – have not been available for some years and the printed volumes of the Official Report are not produced until a revision process for the debate is completed. As a result, paper versions of the debate are not yet available for research purposes; even when they are, their basis will still derive from the original XML document. Interestingly, there does not appear to be a PDF of replies to the written questions – a step that would be taken if the debate were to be physically printed - although there is a PDF of the questions themselves, so for practical or other reasons, the cultural primacy of the printed text seems to be waning on the side of the written questions at least.

There is also the question of data as they are reused outside the Oireachtas. The Official Report data are freely available and people outside the Oireachtas may reuse them with minimal restrictions. For example, kildarestreet.com reuses the data to present debate text in a process independent of the Oireachtas, notable mainly in different presentations of search processes or the ability of users to make comments. However, as the source data are the same, there appears no reason to deviate from using what is produced by the Debates Office. The methods of this making available of Oireachtas data, however, also speaks to wider considerations to be addressed in the research.

Open(ing) Data

The Oireachtas operates an open data portal at data.oireachtas.ie or at the application programming interface api.oireachtas.ie, where users or machine inquiries can return data in JSON form. The portal currently returns datasets for legislation, constituencies and parties, for example, as well as debates-specific data such as divisions – votes taken in the Houses – and plenary debates information. As described, it is intended to use the Postman API development platform to query this resource as it allows more versatility in making additional or customised queries.

The primary plenary debate dataset that the research will address, in addition to the May 11 XML document outlined above, is returned with the following REST query:

```
GET:https://api.oireachtas.ie/v1/debates?chamber_type=house&chamber_id=&chamber
=dail&date_start=2021-05-11&date_end=2021-05-11&limit=500
```

This returns a JSON with objects that include debate section headings, speaker and speech counts, URIs for speakers and debates etc.

Similarly, the REST query:

```
GET:https://api.oireachtas.ie/v1/questions?date_start=2021-05-11&date_end=2021-05-11&limit=5000&qtype=oral,written
```

is used to return the written questions dataset for 11 May, or the query can be adjusted as necessary for other dates. Postman can also be used to return the appropriate XML document through the REST query:

```
GET: https://data.oireachtas.ie/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/mul@/main.xml
```

and variations of same according to date etc. The research will primarily focus on the XML document and the two JSONs returned from the three REST queries above, which specifically relate to the available Debates Office datasets for 11 May on the Oireachtas open data portal.

Finding Data and Leveraging the Oireachtas Web Ontology

Plenary Debate JSON

Both the JSONs and the XML document returned from these initial queries are typical examples of Debates Office data structured with the Oireachtas data ontology as influenced by the Web Ontology Language, OWL, and European Legislative Identifier, ELI. For the plenary dataset, JSON data are structured in a multilevel hierarchy with “debateRecord” at the highest level and nested object and array entries for information such as date, formats, chamber, bill or speech counts and URI information for the debate in question.

The top levels of the JSON returned for the plenary debate of 11 May are as follows in a nested tree view:

```
object          {1}
  debateRecord  {9}
    date       : 2021-05-11
    debateSections [31]
    lastUpdated : 2021-06-05T01:33:46+01:00
```

```

debateType      :      debate
formats         {3}
chamber        {2}
counts         {5}
house          {6}
uri            :      https://data.oireachtas.ie/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/main

```

Working in the Sublime Text code editor it is possible to explore the nested structure by following the Oireachtas data ontology as outlined on the GitHub repository.

The “formats” object comprises:

```

"formats": {
  "pdf": {
    "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/mul@/main.pdf"
  },
  "xml": {
    "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/mul@/main.xml"
  },
  "writtens_pdf": null
},

```

This provides the URIs for both the PDF and XML document for the debate.

Exploring the “counts” object also provides information related to debates:

```

"counts": {
  "questionCount": 27,
  "billCount": 0,
  "divisionCount": 0,
  "contributorCount": 149,
  "debateSectionCount": 31
},

```

However, most of the pertinent data for parliamentary debates are nested under the “debateSections” array. As the above data indicate, there are 31

sections of debate, each labelled as “debateSection” and within an identically structured object exemplified in the following:

```

"debateSection": {
    "debateType": "questions",
    "formats": {
        "pdf": null,
        "xml": {
            "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-
05-11/debate/mul@/dbsect_2.xml"
        }
    },
    "showAs": "Ceisteanna ó Cheannairí - Leaders' Questions",
    "containsDebate": true,
    "parentDebateSection": null,
    "counts": {
        "speakerCount": 6,
        "speechCount": 34
    },
    "speakers": [],
    "debateSectionId": "dbsect_2",
    "bill": null,
    "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-
11/debate/dbsect_2"
}

```

In each of these objects and the (empty) array we can see the possibility of leveraging the metadata assigned to debate elements. Again, there are simple counts of speakers and number of contributions with the “speakerCount” and “speechCount” tags and there is a URI for the debate section, although unfortunately this address always returns an error when queried. The “showAs” tag indicates the business conducted and there is array for “speakers”, which, unfortunately, is always returned as empty when operating within the current constraints of the REST query method.

Once the JSON can be parsed, the data can be cleaned or trimmed if necessary either with specific data wrangling or cleaning applications such as OpenRefine before being used with other applications or platforms. This is in preference to simple spreadsheet applications such as Excel, as at all times it is imperative that the data are not changed beyond cleaning, trimming or reordering because an overarching goal is to “re-present” data rather than present new data. This could be especially difficult in cases where the data have to be transferred between applications or, in particular, when the machine-generated JSON must be cleaned, trimmed or otherwise adjusted manually. In such cases, a data validation step involving resources such as the jsonformatter.org website is invaluable when used with both the source data and tools like the Sublime Text code editor.

Although the “speakers” array contains an empty string as produced by the Oireachtas API, it is important to note how this could provide a useful way of linking debates data. Oireachtas Members are identified by URI and this in turn links to other data, including constituencies and parties. It may also provide a link to data outside the Oireachtas, including social media profiles and, most interestingly, the linked data for political or parliamentary bodies such as the European Parliament, as described in the work of van Aggelen et al. (2017) with *LinkedEP*.

The most conspicuous absence, however, if we are trying to work with Dáil debates, is an object or array with debate text beyond that of a section or question heading. It is possible that such data could be included within a speakers array but this may not be practical. It is also unfortunate that debate section URIs do not seem to function as one might have hoped. As such, structured debate text is only available from the XML document.

Written Questions JSON

The JSON returned for a query of written answers differs slightly from that returned for the plenary session in the way objects are nested. The structure is as follows:

```
{
  "question": {
    "date": "2021-05-13",
    "debateSection": {
      "formats": {
        "pdf": null,
        "xml": {
          "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-13/debate/mul@dbsect_4.xml"
        }
      }
    },
    "showAs": "Defence Forces",
    "debateSectionId": "dbsect_4",
    "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-13/debate/dbsect_4"
  },
  "showAs": " 1. Deputy John Brady asked the Minister for Defence the reviews that have taken place to date of the 1994 Defence Forces service contracts, which have contributed to the retention crisis in the Defence Forces. [25008/21] ",
  "by": {
    "memberCode": "John-Brady.D.2016-10-03",
    "showAs": "John Brady",
    "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/member/id/John-Brady.D.2016-10-03"
  },
  "to": {
    "showAs": "Defence",
    "roleCode": null,
    "roleType": null,
    "uri": null
  },
  "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/question/2021-05-13/pq_1",
  "house": {
    "showAs": "33rd Dáil",
    "chamberType": "house",

```

```

    "committeeCode": "",
    "houseCode": "dail",
    "houseNo": "33",
    "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/house/dail/33"
  },
  "questionType": "oral",
  "questionNumber": 1
},
"contextDate": "2021-05-13"
}

```

Although it shares many of the attribute-value pairs of the plenary JSON, it has other data specifically related to questions, including “questionType”, “questionNumber”, the Member asking in the form of a “by” object, the responding Minister in the form of a “to” object and both the question in full and an assigned heading under “showAs” in different objects. Of particular interest is how the extra data in the form of the full question text, a question heading and speaker identification can be leveraged and how this may change the process of discerning meaning from each of these JSON formats. Also of note is the fact that no single XML document for replies to written answers is produced; separate XML documents are produced for individual questions.

Plenary XML

The Oireachtas data ontology as it applies to debate text, as opposed to the structure of debates, can be seen more clearly in the XML document. The initial sections of the document comprise the technical aspects applied, demonstrating the influence of OWL and ELI ontologies and the Akoma Ntoso schema:

```

<akomaNtoso xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
xmlns="http://docs.oasis-open.org/legaldocml/ns/akn/3.0/CSD13"
xsi:schemaLocation="http://docs.oasis-open.org/legaldocml/ns/akn/3.0/CSD13
.akomantoso30.xsd">

```

```

<debate name="Official Report">
  <meta>
    <identification source="#debates">
      <FRBRWork>
        <FRBRthis value="/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/main"/>
        <FRBRuri value="/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate"/>
        <FRBRdate date="2021-05-11" name="#generation"/>
        <FRBRauthor as="#author" href="/ie/oireachtas/house/dail/33"/>
        <FRBRcountry value="ie"/>
        <FRBRname value="debate"/>
      </FRBRWork>
      <FRBRExpression>
        <FRBRthis value="/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/mul@/main"/>
        <FRBRuri value="/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/mul@"/>
        <FRBRdate date="2021-05-11" name="#reported"/>
        <FRBRauthor as="#editor" href="#debates"/>
        <FRBRlanguage language="eng"/>
      </FRBRExpression>
      <FRBRManifestation>
        <FRBRthis value="/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/mul@/main.xml"/>
        <FRBRuri value="/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/mul@.akn"/>
        <FRBRdate date="2021-06-05" name="#publication"/>
        <FRBRauthor as="#editor" href="#debates"/>
      </FRBRManifestation>
    </identification>
  </meta>
</debate>

```

First, we can consider an exchange between three Members – Deputy Mary Lou McDonald, An Ceann Comhairle and the Taoiseach – in the following excerpt:

```

<speech by="#MaryLouMcDonald" eld="spk_11">
  <from>Deputy Mary Lou McDonald<recordedTime time="2021-05-11T14:10:00+01:00"/></from>
  <p eld="para_22">What is the Taoiseach doing about investment funds?</p>
</speech>

```

```

<speech by="#SeanOFearghailFF" eld="spk_12">
  <from> An Ceann Comhairle<recordedTime time="2021-05-11T14:10:00+01:00"/></from>
  <p eld="para_23">Allow the Taoiseach without interruption.</p>
</speech>
<speech by="#MichaelMartin" eld="spk_13">
  <from> The Taoiseach<recordedTime time="2021-05-11T14:10:00+01:00"/></from>
  <p eld="para_24">Sinn Féin seems to be objecting to housing project after housing project for a
  variety of reasons, perhaps just to mess up the whole thing and prevent success. In terms of the investment
  funds-----</p>
</speech>

```

We can see the metatag labelling of elements of speech within `<speech>` tags and within that we can see the specific ontology applied to speaker names, identified in `<from>` tags. In the example above, the eID of `#MaryLouMcDonald` is applied and at the beginning of the XML document, under a `<references>` tag, the eID is linked to other information for the Member, including a value derived from date of first election:

```

<TLCPerson eld="MaryLouMcDonald" href="/ie/oireachtas/member/id/Mary-Lou-McDonald.D.2011-03-09" showAs="Mary Lou McDonald"/>

```

Also to be noted is the labelling of contributions following the pattern "spk_1", which should not be confused with the number of discrete speakers. The 31 debate sections are, as expected, within the `<debateSection>` tags seen in the plenary JSON, and these are within `<debateBody>` and `<debate>` tags, respectively. Debate text is broken down to paragraph level, with contributions at paragraph level receiving an eID:

```

<p eld="para_117">People in Castletownbere and Unionhall are stretched to the last.
The Taoiseach was asleep at the wheel during Brexit.</p>

```

Headings for debates are in a `<heading>` tag and it should be noted that headings given to formal parliamentary questions tabled orally – as opposed to those replied to with written answers in a written format – share the same `<heading>` tag, despite the question headings being subordinate

in the hierarchy in a practical sense. Note the lack of differentiation between the main headings “Ceisteanna (Atógáil) – Questions (Resumed)” and “Ceisteanna ar Sonraíodh Uain Dóibh – Priority Questions” versus the procedurally subordinate question heading “Foreign Conflicts”:

```
<debateSection name="questions" eld="dbsect_13">
  <heading>Ceisteanna (Atógáil) - Questions (Resumed)<recordedTime time="2021-05-11T20:10:00+01:00"/></heading>
</debateSection>
<debateSection name="questions" eld="dbsect_14">
  <heading>Ceisteanna ar Sonraíodh Uain Dóibh - Priority Questions<recordedTime time="2021-05-11T20:10:00+01:00"/></heading>
<debateSection name="question" eld="dbsect_15">
  <heading>Foreign Conflicts<recordedTime time="2021-05-11T20:10:00+01:00"/></heading>
  <question by="#JohnBrady" to="#Foreign" eld="pq_47">
    <p eld="para_653">47. <b>Deputy John Brady</b> asked the <b>Minister for Foreign Affairs</b> the actions he plans to take on the international stage to put a halt to the support being offered to the Ethiopian Government and Eritrean forces engaged in a systematic campaign of violence in Tigray by the United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia, particularly given Ireland's long partnership with Ethiopia and role on the United Nations Security Council. [24129/21]</p>
  </question>
```

In this example we can also see the question mechanics as used in the written questions JSON, specifically those referring to question, number, the Deputy who tabled the question, the Government department to which it is directed and the text of the question itself.

Also of interest in the XML document is how procedural text, or text that would not be attributable to a speaker, is dealt with. This is identified with an eID put in <summary> tags as in the following example:

```
<summary eld="sum_10">Amendment put.</summary>
```

Absent from this XML document is an example of how House divisions, or votes, are dealt with as no votes took place in the Dáil on 11 May 2021.

Vote datasets are available on the Oireachtas API; a REST query via Postman:

```
GET:https://api.oireachtas.ie/v1/divisions?chamber_type=house&chamber_id=&chamber
=dail&date_start=2021-05-11&date_end=2021-05-11&limit=50&outcome=
```

returns the following JSON as confirmation:

```
{
  "head": {
    "counts": {
      "divisionCount": 0,
      "resultCount": 0
    },
    "dateRange": {
      "start": "2021-05-11T00:00:00.000Z",
      "end": "2021-05-11T00:00:00.000Z"
    },
    "lang": "mul"
  },
  "results": [] }
```

Working With Data, Finding Capta, Linking Debate

Once the data have been parsed, the elements most useful to interpreting the text of debates – what is said by Members in debates – can be identified and the parts less useful to the research can be deprioritised or omitted. In the preliminary work on the data, however, the approach should be to work with the entire dataset in OpenRefine or Tableau Prep Builder in order to prepare the data for use rather than trim or clean the JSON datasets and XML document, particularly if that process is destructive. In any case, because the data are excellently structured, minimal cleaning or changing should be required for any of the research processes.

The plenary JSON contains data most pertinent to debates within the “debateSections” array, which comprises 31 “debateSection” objects. Of the data contained in these objects, the most relevant are “debateType”,

which indicates the type of business; "showAs", which gives a description of the business being debated; "counts", which gives the number of speakers and contributions; and the "speakers" array, which is potentially an important element but, unfortunately, empty in the returned JSON. Other elements of the JSON relate more to the technical ordering of the debate or semantic web considerations such as URI addresses.

The written questions JSON, meanwhile, contains some richer debates-related data as described, including the identity of the Deputy asking the question, the Minister responding, question numbers and subject headings in nested objects within the questions array as "by", "to", "questionType", "questionNumber" or "question", for example. Of note is that these object names, readable by people, sit alongside member codes and URIs used for relating information to other data.

As described, the XML document follows the Akoma Ntoso schema, with some overlap of tags, including <debateSection> or <question>; however, the relative position of debate would mainly be calculated from <debateSection> eIDs, as well as the contributor, speech and paragraph eIDs. The debate text is contained at its most granular level at those <p> sections tagged with a paragraph eID.

There is overlap between the JSON data and the XML document that contains the text of the debate and it is possible, as explained, to correlate different sections of debate as a result. However, it is unfortunate that the speakers array in the plenary JSON is empty, as it could have provided some of the richer speaker and speech contexts that can only be derived from the XML document as it stands. This appears to be a restriction in the REST process as instanced by the Oireachtas and while it is possible to change it, it should be noted that the LiPad project makes available a complete PostgreSQL dump of Canadian debates data. The Oireachtas uses

the same PostgreSQL process, in conjunction with ElasticSearch, so making its data available in a similar way would allow a researcher to tailor requests to specific needs without intervention from the Oireachtas.

Both the JSON datasets and the XML document are required, therefore, to get a complete picture of the marked-up debate from 11 May. The written questions JSON, however, in the absence of a unified XML document for written replies, may give an indication of whether extra information in a JSON can approach equal value to the more richly detailed XML document.

<Digital>Tools and Artefact</Digital>

Starting

Once the data wrangling and parsing of the most useful elements of the May 11 debate are complete, the data can be deployed in various scenarios and on different platforms in order to test outcomes. The digital artefact supporting this research takes the form of an online notebook, a subdomain of the academic portfolio changingconversations.net, detailing the work with the datasets outlined above, showing work with data, testing workflows or visualisations and putting some exploration of a visual epistemological approach online. Where appropriate, there are links to data wrangling on GitHub or in an Observable notebook, for example.

The initial stages of tool exploration involved a comprehensive exploration of the datasets. Text, either from the Oireachtas web page or the datasets themselves, could be uploaded directly to a resource like Voyant Tools for textual analysis; platforms like MeaningCloud and Google Natural Language appeared to be more commercially focused and were deprioritised as a result. A project detailing topic modelling for the text of an Oireachtas committee may serve as a substitute consideration (Rigney, 2016).

JSON data could be used with OpenRefine and Tableau Prep Builder in their native structure but the XML document required conversion to a comma-separated value, CSV, dataset in order to reconcile the data between JSONs and the XML document, and this had mixed results. It was possible, for example, to have columns with paragraph, speaker, name and debate body values, which could be reconciled with the JSON values, but null values and conversion errors could introduce inaccuracies.

Paragraph	Speaker No	Name	Debate Body
			in respect of Palestine, finally acts.
			of over 12,000 apartments and homes in Dublin city owned by institutional investors showed ti
			on Sunday that American tourists who have been fully vaccinated against Covid-19 will be abl
			, a motion re financial resolution on the Private Security Services (Amendment) Bill, on Wednes
			, every night; and in how households in Ireland put candles in the window to honour all those w
			, in which any Deputy can stand up and say he or she believes we should have a debate on th
			.
			. I assume similar content was bought in other Sunday newspapers. Perhaps the Minister coul
			. Now, because of the public anger, they are running around like headless chickens. There are
			. Subsequent to that contribution, the regulator issued a deluge of diatribe to the press saying t
) the sitting schedule for a Tuesday shall apply to a Wednesday, where the first day of a sitting
			document (Department of Housing, 2016b: 17), for example, highlights the benefits of institutio
			I put that to the regulator, from whom I received no response. I am not alone in my view on the
para_1	spk_1	Deputy Mary Lou McDonald	At the weekend, the Taoiseach stated that housing is the number one crisis facing young peop
para_2			It is not lost on these young people, their parents or their grandparents that the housing crisis
para_3			At a time when the Government should be moving heaven and earth to do everything possible
para_4			Moreover, they are not stopping with Dublin; their plan is now to spread their wings across the
para_5			All of this happens against the backdrop of the publication of the utterly discredited Affordable
para_6			There are things the Government could do right now to make housing more affordable. It coul

Figure 3: Detail of XML data as loaded into MS Excel via export

JSON data, meanwhile, may be loaded natively into OpenRefine and Tableau Prep Builder, as well as Tableau Desktop. Headings should be renamed in a non-destructive way in order to make comparisons or load data into visualisations. At this stage it was possible to derive high-level meaning from debates, such as word or character counts, numbers of speakers, numbers of questions asked, while grouping Members speaking in specific debates etc.

With the written questions dataset, for example, the Member asking, departments and the questions themselves could be loaded and visualised in Tableau Desktop in a short workflow:

Figure 4: Detail of PQ JSON data visualised in Tableau Desktop

One of the more versatile workflows involved importing the JSONs to d3.js via an Observable notebook and working to derive meaning via direct coding. The following example groups the plenary JSON data by debate heading:

```
jsonData = ▼Object {
  Name: "May"
  Children: ▼Array(31) [
    0: ▼Object {
      debateType: "questions"
      formats: ►Object {pdf: null, xml: Object}
      showAs: "Ceisteanna ó Cheannairí - Leaders' Questions"
      containsDebate: true
      parentDebateSection: null
      counts: ►Object {speakerCount: 6, speechCount: 34}
      speakers: ►Array(0) []
      debateSectionId: "dbsect_2"
      bill: null
      uri: "https://data.oireachtas.ie/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/dbsect_2"
    }
    1: ▼Object {
      debateType: "orderofBusiness"
      formats: ►Object {pdf: null, xml: Object}
      showAs: "An tÓrd Gnó - Order of Business"
      containsDebate: true
      parentDebateSection: null
      counts: ►Object {speakerCount: 16, speechCount: 98}
      speakers: ►Array(0) []
      debateSectionId: "dbsect_3"
      bill: null
      uri: "https://data.oireachtas.ie/akn/ie/debateRecord/dail/2021-05-11/debate/dbsect_3"
    }
    2: ►Object {debateType: "motion", formats: Object, showAs: "Protection of Young Persons (Employment) (Exclusi
```

Figure 5: Detail of plenary debate JSON data wrangled with the d3.js JavaScript library

Building

In working with the datasets in resources like Excel, Tableau, Observable and other platforms, such as Flourish and RAW Graphs, two characteristics of the debate become clear. The first is the importance of hierarchy both in the data structure and the nature of the political debate. The second, as suggested by the Observable example above, is the idea that relating the data, and specifically network characteristics, could be integral to a visual epistemological approach. The value of networks has been suggested by Drucker (2015), and the value of the Oireachtas ontology becomes clear in this way. In particular, the URIs assigned to Members serve to link data across the Oireachtas and leave potential for use in an RDF process.

An experiment in relating both these network and hierarchy elements used the Gephi network visualisation platform and a dataset returned from the Oireachtas open data portal with the query:

```
GET:https://api.oireachtas.ie/v1/members?date_start=1900-01-01&chamber_id=&chamber=dail&date_end=2099-01-01&limit=9999
```

to create an explorable network of all Dáil Members, totalling thousands of entries, since the First Dáil, including characteristics of party and constituency, with gender added manually to an empty object in the dataset returned for each Dáil Deputy.

Figure 6: Detail of historical Members JSON data visualised in Gephi

Once these links were established, the datasets could be further refined. It became clear, for example, that using the *d3.hierarchy*, *d3.group* or *d3.rollup* features in the d3.js library afforded more versatile use of the datasets and moulded data in a way that allowed further visual exploration.

Changing

Working with the data in different forums without alteration can be challenging. Instead of deleting or omitting portions, therefore, it is preferable to use the methods outlined above to group the datasets in a particular way rather than trim or omit data, except in required cases of correction. However, it is worth reiterating that the intention is for the data to be “re-presented”, as Drucker espouses in her advocacy of a visual epistemology. As indicated, the most obvious complication is the possibility of a “disconnect” between the data as presented in the XML document for the plenary session and what is presented in the plenary JSON. Some of the processes will involve interpolating elements of one dataset into the other – speaker identity and the text of debate being the most obvious – and this undoubtedly leaves the potential for errors to be introduced, although such risks may be acceptable if datasets can be improved.

Analysis and Discussion

Dissecting Discourse

Political Discourse and Networks

The Dáil debate from 11 May could form a rich base from which to formulate the visual epistemological approach espoused by Drucker precisely because of the extensive nature of its marking-up in line with, if not exactly according to, semantic web standards. The JSON datasets in particular lend themselves to versatility in testing and use, especially when inputted to applications or platforms where such datasets can be used natively and without further formatting or conversion. The XML document, meanwhile, is a good example of text being richly marked up with descriptive tagging that can be used to break down a large corpus of approximately 80,000 words covering more than eight hours of debate to a fine granularity.

An initial example of the utility and versatility afforded by Oireachtas open datasets can be seen with the Gephi network visualisation of all Dáil Members from 1919 onwards at <https://bubcass.github.io/DH/dail/>. This visualisation and variations are made possible because the data in each Member's returned object are extensive and allows for expansion; note in the following example how the gender key-value pair is empty but allows for data insertion:

```
{
  "member": {
    "memberCode": "Leo-Varadkar.D.2007-06-14",
    "lastName": "Varadkar",
    "firstName": "Leo",
    "gender": "",
    "dateOfDeath": null,
    "fullName": "Leo Varadkar",
    "pld": "LeoVaradkar",
```

```

"wikiTitle": null,

"uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/member/id/Leo-
Varadkar.D.2007-06-14",

"memberships": [
  {
    "membership": {
      "represents": [
        {
          "represent": {
            "representCode": "Dublin-West",
            "showAs": "Dublin West",
            "uri":
"https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/house/dail/30/constituency/Dublin-West",
            "representType": "constituency"
          }
        }
      ],
    },
  },
  {
    "dateRange": {
      "start": "2007-06-14",
      "end": "2011-02-01"
    },
  },
  {
    "offices": [],
    "parties": [
      {
        "party": {
          "showAs": "Fine Gael",
          "dateRange": {
            "start": "2007-05-24",
            "end": "2011-02-01"
          },
        },
        "partyCode": "Fine_Gael",
        "uri":
"https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/party/dail/30/Fine_Gael"
      }
    ]
  }
]

```

```

    ],
    "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/member/id/Leo-Varadkar.D.2007-06-14/house/dail/30",
    "house": {
      "showAs": "30th Dáil",
      "chamberType": "house",
      "houseCode": "dail",
      "houseNo": "30",
      "uri": "https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/house/dail/30"
    }
  }
}
]
}
}

```

The Gephi visualisation only uses the data entries for name, party, constituency and gender, which has been manually coded into the above JSON, but this demonstrates the visualisation possibilities from graphing networks of connections for Dáil Members.

There are further possibilities in linking these data to other datasets, as demonstrated by Shadbolt et al. (2012). For example, by linking the parliamentary question JSONs for the entirety of the Thirty-second Dáil – in the absence of being able to generate a single JSON because of query limits – it was possible to connect the identities of Members asking questions to the Department of Health, map the number of questions to individual constituencies and even correlate these to hospital locations and waiting lists. The visualisation is available at <https://digital.changingconversations.net/flourish/>. Using Tableau Prep Builder or OpenRefine and by finding commonalities in the data, such as constituency names, it was therefore possible to connect data from the

Oireachtas, the Ordnance Survey of Ireland and the Health Service Executive.

Figure 7: Detail from Flourish visualisation of number of parliamentary questions tabled relative to constituencies and hospital locations

The data, including the Oireachtas data, for this visualisation are available at Ireland's open data portal at data.gov.ie but it should be noted that they are not linked open data as envisaged by the Berners-Lee and his five star deployment scheme (5 Star Linked Data - Government Linked Data (GLD) Working Group Wiki, 2021). As of August 2021, there are only four datasets achieving five stars on the Ireland open data portal; Oireachtas data achieves a three-star rating. Constituency data in the visualisation had to be related manually using Tableau Prep Builder rather than automatically between datasets and other data were correlated from this point, or in the case of constituency, Member and parliamentary questions, between Oireachtas open data JSONs. Even if the semantic web standards are not

fully realised, the visualisation exemplifies what is possible by networking disparate datum elements.

Political Discourse and Hierarchy

One of the clearer characteristics of these marked-up data is the nested hierarchies inherent in structuring the data. Both the plenary JSON and XML document are built using nested hierarchies over several levels. As with the Gephi visualisation, connections between these datum elements are not fixed as a necessity, and a visual epistemological approach that interpolates the data in different ways implies meaning does not have to be fixed either. As suggested by McGann (2015), the dichotomy of reader and text, subjectivity and objectivity, can be broken by allowing these disparate parts to be moved about while retaining their relationship by means of the data structure.

We can consider as an example an examination of the elements in the parliamentary questions JSON via Tableau Desktop at <https://digital.changingconversations.net/pq/>. The JSON has a wealth of information that can be broken apart to be put back together many different ways; there are Member names and the departments to which they ask questions, the headings assigned by parliamentary reporters to questions and the text of the question itself. A process of discerning meaning from questions can be followed by seeing who has asked questions, how many questions have been asked, the Departments dealing with the questions and various constructions of these data.

For example, simple quantification of the numbers of questions asked by each Deputy on 11 May 2021 may easily be sorted by Members' names, alphabetically, but to bring more order, quantities can be sorted in ascending order and a heat map visualises different quantities. Taking the

numbers on a journey from data to Drucker’s capta, the information can be put in a treemap, breaking the questions down by Department to which the question is directed, for example, in order to bringing another layer of meaning-making through the intervention of a “reader”. Using a circle-packing diagram, it is also possible, via tooltip, to integrate text indicating the name of the Member asking the question, the question heading and even the question text.

Figure 8: Detail of PQ dataset visualised as circle-packed diagram, with further data revealed via tooltip

Such use of the structured data in the parliamentary questions JSON is a useful example of how the meaning derived from a dataset does not have to be fixed and can instead be a product of reading, the “self-production” alluded to by Drucker (2017). However, to consider the question of such a visualisation being “in a relation of equivalence or identity with that which it claims to represent”, it is important to consider the fundamentals of these data – the debate text itself.

Seeing Patterns...

In Text

As indicated, tools that were initially scoped for text analysis, including MeaningCloud and Google's Cloud Natural Language AI, were discounted for several reasons. For example, their commercially driven basis, specifically a focus on getting machines to understand human speech rather than helping humans find meaning in large tracts of human speech, seemed incongruous to the aim of this research in trying to form a visual epistemology for interpreting the Official Report. In addition, these applications required either training or administration in order to reach a level where even basic sentiment analysis could be trialled.

Voyant Tools, meanwhile, offers a "one-stop" shop where a corpus of text can be analysed in several different ways, albeit in a somewhat superficial way. Drucker (2017) argues that text analysis via a platform like Voyant Tools can amount to "processing" instead of reading, and there may be danger in ascribing too much meaning to what is essentially a machined breakdown of text. However, used in conjunction with other methods, there may be value in integrating or at least including text analysis in a visual epistemological approach.

Initial analysis of the text of the plenary debate of 11 May was done by uploading the PDF, as the debate is not available as a single URL on the web. It is possible to input more than one URL at a time for Voyant Tools to analyse but it was decided this could increase potential for errors. However, the URI for the XML document could also be inputted and returned for analysis and several notable improvements on the PDF were immediately noticeable. For example, an artefact from the initial production of the report seemed to be present in the PDF in identifying the speaker, exemplified like so:

11/05/2021B00200The Taoiseach:

This led to the term "05" being misidentified as one of the top five most frequent words in the corpus when analysed as a PDF. The metric of average words per sentence differed greatly because of artefact outliers in the PDF, at 21 words per sentence for the XML document and a rather implausible 90 words per sentence in the PDF. As other artefacts were also noticeable from the analysis of the PDF file, as well as slight changes in word counts etc. arising from titles or header information etc., the XML document was used as the primary source.

These differences in headline metrics for two versions of the same debate should serve as indicating the danger in relying too much on this form of text processing and particularly in trying to derive too much from inappropriate or unsuitable analysis.

For the text of the debate in question, the most useful meaning was derived from the TermsBerry, Bubblelines and Trends tools, themselves visual in nature.

Figure 9: Detail of plenary debate text analysed by Voyant Tools

For example, a major debate on the occasion of Europe Day took place on 11 May, and both the trend line and Bubbleline tools show how incidence of the term “European” increased substantially – literally going off the chart - at this time. Other common words were spread more evenly throughout the day, although it is also notable that the terms “Minister” and “Government” increased during question times, the specific purpose of which is to hold Government leaders to account.

Another possibility is specialised topic modelling (Rigney, 2016), and customisation to the political corpus and even to outputs from the Oireachtas may prove beneficial where readings need to be “closer” in nature, for example.

Without Text

Taking the ideas of networks, hierarchies and the visual capta that may come from the text analysis tools in Voyant, a visual epistemological approach seems to at least initially require elements of all three.

A tidy tree is a simple graphical approach to a hierarchy and suits the hierarchical nature of the plenary JSON. Hierarchies are evident in political debate within the Oireachtas in several ways. Most clearly, a day of plenary debate is broken into the subjects discussed, whether this is regular business like question time or topical issues discussions, the structured debate of dealing with different stages of legislation or other types of parliamentary business, such as statements or matters of procedure. Within those broad-ranging debate headings, there may a further layer of hierarchy, such as when questions or topical issues are assigned headings by reporters, or the hierarchy may merely be on the level of individual speaker, down to the paragraphs identified in the Oireachtas ontology with eIDs.

In a similar way, speakers in a debate can be seen working within a hierarchy, both individually and within the political party and governance system. Parties and the government have leaders and assigned spokespersons, for example, which can add a level to the speaking hierarchy.

We can consider the simple visualisation of this hierarchy, achieved through the d3.js JavaScript library using Observable and by rolling up and grouping the JSON data by headings at:

[https://digital.changingconversations.net/tidy-tree/:](https://digital.changingconversations.net/tidy-tree/)

Figure 10: Detail of plenary debate JSON as tidy tree @Observable

This exemplifies how the flow of debate hierarchy can be visualised through multiple levels in a relatively uncluttered fashion; in this case there is a main heading (Questions – Resumed – Priority Questions), a heading assigned by a reporter to the question (Foreign Conflicts), the interventions of speakers

as identified by title and there is even the possibility of including the text of the individual contributions (spk_ eIDs), although the text is not included in the JSON as retrieved from the API. In this case, the contribution or spk_ eID data were cross-checked with the XML document and added manually. A potential drawback of the tidy tree arises from a characteristic of hierarchies; as they are by definition nested entities, static visualisations of hierarchies tend to use much space. Using JavaScript, however, it is possible to build collapsible hierarchy visualisations, such as with the tidy tree. There may be superior ways to visually present the debate nonetheless.

Changing It - Towards a Visual Epistemology

Radial Dendrogram

[@https://digital.changingconversations.net/radial-dendrogram/](https://digital.changingconversations.net/radial-dendrogram/)

The radial dendrogram may be the clearest evolutionary step in visualising the debate from the tidy tree or the tidy tree's radial sibling. This is still a clear visualisation of the hierarchy but its collapsible nature also serves to highlight the networked nature of the debate. Dynamic highlighting indicates the different sections are apart from each other in form and content but there is no mistaking they are part of a whole.

In this example we have abandoned the linear nature of the debate and Members who contributed to a debate are listed alphabetically, appearing once for each time they contribute to the debate. The plenary JSON contains no speaker information or text of individual contributions, with those contributions identified by means of the spk_ eID from the XML document. Values displayed are the component parts, so a speaker will have two such parts – a title and the spk_ eID element.

Figure 11: Detail of plenary debate JSON as radial dendrogram @Observable

Force-Directed Tree

[@https://digital.changingconversations.net/force/](https://digital.changingconversations.net/force/)

The radial dendrogram is the first example of a visualisation that moves us away from the safety nets of names or titles, or specifically the “logical” chronological flow of “reading” debate. There are debate section labels from the plenary debate JSON but it is not incumbent on the viewer or reader to follow them; in the case of the individual contributions, the lack of text leads us to consider other values, such as how “busy” a section is, including the number of and variation in speakers. If the statements on Europe Day have 25 speaking interventions and Leaders’ Questions saw 34 speaking interventions, how should that be interpreted? What about the identity of speakers and number of times each spoke? In the absence of

text, what is there to give the viewer the cues akin to those in texts? There is no speech content in the JSON but even if there were, how does one situate portions of text outside of a linear context?

We might take these visual characteristics of the radial dendrogram further while completely exploding the linear aspects of the debate with a force-directed tree, which uses a d3.js module that simulates external forces and serves to demonstrate network elements. The hierarchy elements remain plain to see through line connections but this visualisation emphasises the interconnectedness of the actors; instead of speakers appearing in organised isolation, as they might in a tidy tree map, they are quite literally pushed together and forced apart depending on when they contribute to a debate.

Figure 12: Detail of the plenary debate JSON as force-directed tree @Observable

The absence of labels in this visualisation, aside from on a hovering tooltip, serves to emphasise how such networks are not naturally described using language, existing despite and not because of it. The “reader”, meanwhile, has so much control over the debate that it can literally be moved around the screen.

Treemap and Icicle

[@https://digital.changingconversations.net/treemap/](https://digital.changingconversations.net/treemap/)

[@https://digital.changingconversations.net/icicle/](https://digital.changingconversations.net/icicle/)

The force-directed tree indicates the possibilities of seeing the Official Report in a different context because it can be freed from the rules of reading texts while retaining a shape afforded by the structuring of the text as data. The hierarchy retains its importance in indicating the business that takes place and the speakers within. The number of speakers, however, gives no indication of the content, for example, or qualities such as speaker sentiment. Even if text is not a requirement for visualising debate, to discount it is to discount an elemental factor of political discussion.

We can consider, for example, a contrast between the debate sections of “Leaders’ Questions” and “Europe Day: Statements”. The Leaders’ Questions debate, according to the plenary JSON “counts” object, has 34 speaking contributions from just six speakers. Voyant Tools indicates this section of the debate has 6,048 total words and 1,498 unique word forms. The debate on Europe Day, meanwhile, has 20 speakers making 25 speaking contributions over a discussion involving 20,543 words and 3,369 unique word forms; it was a far longer debate and appears much less contentious.

So if we cannot discount the importance of the debate text, is it possible to “visualise” its importance? The treemap construction visualises the “size” of

the debate once values have been assigned, via manual coding of the plenary JSON, in the speaker array that is empty as returned by the Oireachtas API. In this use case, the “showAs” value of a speaker, such as “Deputy Mary Lou McDonald” is assigned a value of the number of written characters in a speaking contribution, although a word count could be assigned in the same way. Short contributions can thus be differentiated, ranging from values as low as 48 characters for some contributions from the Ceann Comhairle during Leaders’ Questions to highs of 19,326 from the Taoiseach in the debate on Europe day. The value of 120,844 indicated for Europe Day statements versus 33,086 indicated for Leaders’ Questions tallies with the Voyant Tools data and is a more concise visualisation of the fragmented nature of the shorter debate.

Figure 13: Detail of Leaders' Questions as treemap, indicating its fragmented nature @Observable

This is another example of a visual approach to debate that uses hierarchy characteristics in preference to a chronological and linear approach for reading, although it should be noted that because the hierarchy functions as a result of structured data, the values for ordering visualisations like the treemap can be changed via d3.js; essentially, it should be possible to reorder such a visualisation by spk_eID in order to read the debate chronologically.

A variation of the treemap is the zoomable icicle example, which indicates several levels of hierarchy at once and demonstrates the value of colour in a visualisation. This gives an even clearer demonstration of the relative lengths or fragmentation of debates, albeit at the expense of using more vertical space.

Sunburst

[@https://digital.changingconversations.net/sunburst/](https://digital.changingconversations.net/sunburst/)

The visualisations thus far can be seen as facilitating exploration of a particular aspect of debate on a day. The interactivity afforded by JavaScript also offers the potential to move from close to distant and hyper reading; the sunburst visualisation, combining network and hierarchy elements, is a good example of being able to move from broad debate headings to individual contributions quickly without losing the shape of the debate.

Edge Bundling

[@https://digital.changingconversations.net/hierarchy1/](https://digital.changingconversations.net/hierarchy1/)

A visual epistemology may prove most effective where language is lacking. The flow of discourse over the course of a debate is not easily described or measured, for example. Parliamentary discourse is organic and only planned within structures of debate proceedings but there is a demonstrable flow

between speakers that may not be easily transposed to text. There is also the question of formal parliamentary debate structures existing in a tension between the public nature of debate and how social media or television can influence parliamentary performance, such as in topical debates or those involving party or Government leaders.

The edge-bundling visualisation goes some way to demonstrating the flow of debate over time by indicating who is speaking in a debate and to whom.

Figure 14: Detail of plenary debate JSON data as edge-bundled hierarchy, grouped by debate heading @Observable

The red lines indicate when a Member is speaking to another Member and the blue lines indicate a Member is being spoken to, without a reply being made. For the most part, debate in the Dáil occurs through the chairperson – the Ceann Comhairle, Leas-Cheann Comhairle or an acting chairperson -

but in cases like Leaders' Questions, the Order of Business or question time, a leading member of the Government would also be addressed, if informally. In this case, most contributions on the Order of Business are addressed to the Taoiseach and the Ceann Comhairle. By hovering over the entries of the Taoiseach or Ceann Comhairle, one can identify where debate occurred formally through the chairperson (blue line) or where there was back-and-forth discourse between Members (red line), which can indicate a contentious debate.

The edge bundling visualisation also demonstrates the hierarchical characteristics of Dáil debate. In the example there are two versions of the visualisation, with one having debate section headings – which serve to “tidy” the debate - and the other omitting those headings, giving an indication of speaker flow across an entire day of debate. This approach, facilitated by the linked nature of Oireachtas data, also allows the additional hierarchical element of party to be introduced, meaning speakers are arranged not by when or why they spoke but by party background.

Limitations

There are many limitations in this research, including but not limited to the following. It is a cautious first step towards moving the way we take meaning from political debate from what is not only written down but written down in a particular way and in a certain format. It takes the view that while the text of political debate is important, it is one of several document dynamics that might be considered in deriving meaning. Therefore, the first limitation may be a question of suitability or acceptance. It should be noted that a visual epistemological approach should not necessarily be seen as something to replace convention; its function, at least initially, may therefore be as a complement to more conventional readings of political discourse.

The clearest limitation to the outlined epistemological approach is a move away from using the text of a debate. As indicated, this is partially a consequence of the Oireachtas API requests not returning content in the “speakers” array, although the presence of an array in the first place means it is likely this could be changed. If the speaker data from the XML document could be included in the plenary JSON, for example, it should be possible to integrate text from spk_ eIDs into interactive visualisations such as the treemap or radial dendrogram described.

There is also a limitation in the current research as it is constrained to one day of debate. This arises because in order to use the Oireachtas data with assets like the d3.js JavaScript library, the JSONs in particular had to be altered manually to include elements like speaker identification and data in a laborious process.

In order to scale visualisations, it is necessary to either have the data available via the Oireachtas JSONs changed automatically or have the source data available with all the required elements, as it is with the Canadian parliamentary corpus. As indicated, it may be possible for Oireachtas data to either be made available as a PostgreSQL data dump or even have the open data parameters changed to include speaker and speech data that would yield a more complete visual approach.

Connected to this is the question of appropriate visualisations. The visualisation examples for the proposed epistemology are by no means exhaustive and as the relationship between “capta” and “reader” are necessarily fluid, as described by Hayles (2016), among others, there is likely no single approach to visualising parliamentary debate. There is a great difference in what meaning can be derived from the edge-bundling approach versus the tidy tree, for example, and at its heart such a process is dependent on the reader.

Conclusion

Entombed in a Shrine of Zeros and Ones

The title of this research is inspired from a monologue given by Don Draper, a fictitious advertising executive from the television serial “Mad Men” (Mad Men, 2009). In the same speech where he implores a client to “change the conversation” he argues:

Change is neither good nor bad; it simply is.

The nature of political discourse is of constant change, an imperfect reflection of society, its people and their aspirations, worries and desires. Despite its characteristic flux, the presence of political discourse is nevertheless constant and immutable. If it is not going anywhere, and if the political sphere reflects constant change, with new politicians put continuously in place of those rejected, why has our “reading” of this discourse remained relatively static? Why have we not changed the nature of this conversation as the world around it has evolved? This research is intended as a first step towards such change, a move away from the hegemony of the printed word to other approaches to “reading” texts, facilitated by digital advances.

Since the first entry to the Official Report of the Houses of the Oireachtas thousands of Members have been elected to Leinster House, political parties have come and gone and the political machine has facilitated countless changes in Irish society. The manner in which the Official Report is produced has evolved to a great extent and it is now “born digital” but the act of “reading” these political debates is largely unchanged. The word as it is printed on paper reigns. Hayles (2010) argues that print and digital run in parallel but the messages from each side cannot seem to traverse the barrier between them. It may be the case that for a visual epistemological approach to take hold, people holding the conversation will have to build

trust in possible alternatives to reading a corpus only as a printed text. It is a leap that may be difficult to bridge.

This research has touched on big data (Kitchin, 2014) but rather than suffering the problems noted by some (Schöch, 2013), the harnessing of a extensively structured textual data could illustrate the advantages of big data characteristics in interpreting texts; the Oireachtas is a good example of outputting both “big” and “smart” data, so an approach to harness both characteristics seems logical.

From this we can consider the reader as actor. An exciting possibility of this type of epistemological approach is that the reader would become a much more active contributor to how debates are even assembled before being read. The visual examples in the research may each suit particular readings but not all. For example, the edge-bundling technique indicates flow of a debate; the treemap facilitates movement between the types of close, distant and hyper reading described by Hayles; and the force-directed tree emphasises the networked characteristics of a debate. The addition of the debate text to examples like the treemap or sunburst visualisation would improve their versatility but without impacting on their visual worth because of their interactive hierarchical construction. As with projects like the Digital Panopticon (*The Digital Panopticon: Tracing London Convicts in Britain and Australia, 1780-1925*, 2021), the intervention of the reader in how to visualise the text is paramount to interpretation. The data should not change but the meaning could.

This also relates to the question of opening the data to the masses.

Oireachtas data are already available via the open data portal for reuse in fulfilment of a European directive but to truly realise its potential, the data should not only be available but usable in a practical sense by members of the public. Visualisations of aspects of the Official Report, such as those in

this paper exploring parliamentary questions, may be an example not only of making these data more easily available but also more palatable to a wider audience.

There is also the question of scaling such an approach. This research dealt with debate from just one day of debate but the Official Report comprises thousands of days of proceedings going back decades. It is a continually updated corpus. This epistemological approach, however, should welcome more data and its meaning-making could become even richer if it could be applied across different and longer periods.

The Official Report functions as a tool to hold public representatives to account, to be used by the people who elected them. However, the debates were for decades only available to read in the printed books of the Official Report, and it was only with the introduction of television cameras and, later, its publication on the web that Irish parliamentary debate became available to much wider audiences. People can now “see” these debates much more easily but how they take meaning from them is still influenced by what people say or write elsewhere; instead of this just happening in academic journals or newspapers, it is now happening on splintered forms of social and other media as well.

Now, more than ever, it is vital that we “show the data” of these debates. Instead of a closed book, the potential for meaning-making may now be caged in an indecipherable JSON. If Dáil debates have lived for decades as pages in heavy books, they may be now “entombed in a shrine of zeros and ones” (St. Vincent, 2013). A visual epistemological approach may help people make that meaning. It could help change that conversation.

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